

Letters to the Editor

In the December, 1966, issue of the Journal of the Indian Chemical Society (vol. 43, p. 772) Dr. K. K. Tripathi and Dr. R. K. Patnaik have published a paper on the citrate complexes of chromium (III). Having gone through this paper I feel it necessary to convey the following pertinent views :

The pH-titration technique used by the authors, and in fact any other similar procedure, for evaluating formation constants of complexes is only applicable in a labile system in which equilibrium is established instantaneously at each stage of titration. The rate of formation of chromium (III) — citrate complexes, which is the forward rate governing the rate of attainment of the equilibrium, is known to be very slow. At 25°C the rate-constant for this reaction is about $2.3 \times 10^{-3} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ (R. E. Hamm *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 80, 4469.), which means that it will take several days for the equilibrium to be established in this system at room temperature. The results on the pH-titration of a solution containing citric acid and Cr(III) perchlorate cannot therefore yield any information on the equilibrium constants for Cr(III) — citrate complex-formation. The shift in the pH-titration curve for citric acid in presence of Cr(III) is evidently chiefly due to consumption of alkali by the aquo-chromium (III) ion forming hydroxo-complexes, a fact well established and is also apparent from the appearance of deep green color of the solution during titration. This reaction being of the acid-base type involving no rupture of the Cr(III) — ligand (oxygen atom of coordinated water in this case) bond is instantaneous, unlike the one involving replacement of one ligand by another (like the replacement of water by citrate as in the formation of citrate complexes) in Cr(III) complexes. These important points have been completely overlooked by the authors.

Again, the value of the first hydrolysis constant for aquo-chromium (III) ion determined by the authors is 4.58×10^{-1} . However, the value of this constant according to a number of independent investigators (Cf. "*Stability Constants of Metal Ion Complexes*", p. 48, Special Publication No. 17, The Chemical Society, London, 1964) is of the order of 10^{-6} under comparable conditions. This clearly reveals a complete lack of precision in the data given by Tripathi and Patnaik, arising chiefly out of faulty assumptions. It is also important to mention that the hydrolysis constant of an aquo-metal ion can only be determined in a non-complexing medium in the absence of complexing ligands. No meaningful value for the true hydrolysis constant for aquo-chromium (III) ion can be obtained from observations on solutions of CrCl_3 which contain chloro-aquo-chromium (III) ions and not the aquo-chromium (III) ion. But even for the chloro-aquo-chromium (III) ions the hydrolysis constant reported in the literature (Cf. "*Stability Constants of Metal Ion Complexes*", p. 49, loc. cit) is of the order of 10^{-6} . Hence, the data quoted by the authors in support of their finding is of no relevance.

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AN ADDENDUM

STUDIES IN THE FORMATION AND PROPERTIES OF CARBON-OXYGEN SURFACE COMPLEXES: PART I. FORMATION OF THE COMPLEXES ON TREATMENT OF CHARCOAL WITH DIFFERENT OXIDISING AGENTS

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The following Tables (I-IV) refer to the paper published in *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, Vol. 44, No. 1, 1967, p. 64.

TABLE I

Oxygen content, base adsorption capacity and bromine fixation of the original sugar charcoal before and after the various treatments

Description of the sample	Oxygen evolved on degassing at 1200° as (g./100 g.)			Total oxygen evolved as CO ₂ , CO & H ₂ O on degassing at 1200° (g./100g.)	Loss in weight during treatment (g./100g.)	Base adsorption capacity (m.c./100g.)	Non-titratable CO ₂ complex (m.c./100g.)	Fixation of bromine (m.c./100g.)
	CO ₂	CO	H ₂ O					
Before any treatment	10.7	8.6	7.7	27.0	—	665 (669)	nil	45
After treatment with acidified pot. permulphate.	15.6	8.6	8.9	33.1	0.19	970 (975)	nil	—
After treatment with chlorine water.	14.1	8.8	7.7	30.6	%	902 (881)	nil	—
After treatment with hydrogen peroxide.	13.1	8.8	7.2	29.1	nil	810 (819)	nil	—
After treatment with acidified pot. permanganate.	10.8	8.7	7.4	26.9	2.1	661 (675)	nil	—
After treatment with oxygen at 400°.	5.4	8.4	7.9	21.7	48.0	333 (338)	nil	190 (206)
After treatment with nitrogen dioxide, at 400°.	8.2	8.5	8.0	24.7	33.0	505 (512)	nil	123 (120)
After treatment with superheated steam at 1000°.	2.0	nil	2.4	4.4	85.0	27 (125)	98	240 (261)

TABLE II

Oxygen content, base adsorption capacity and bromine fixation of the 400°-degassed sugar charcoal before and after the various treatments

Description of the sample	Oxygen evolved on degassing at 1200° as:			Total oxygen evolved as CO ₂ , CO & H ₂ O on degassing at 1200°	Loss in weight during treatment	Base adsorption capacity.	Non-titration CO ₂ -complex	Fixation of bromine
	(g./100 g.)							
	CO ₂	CO	H ₂ O					
Before any treatment.	9.7	6.7	5.6	16.0	—	228 (231)	nil	258
After treatment with acidified pot. persulphate.	7.4	6.9	5.2	19.5	negligible	219 (462)	243	nil (13)
After treatment with chlorine water.	5.3	6.8	5.7	17.8	—	326 (331)	nil	255 (256)
After treatment with hydrogen peroxide.	9.7	6.4	5.4	15.5	nil	236 (231)	nil	260 (256)
After treatment with acidified pot. permanganate.	9.7	6.8	5.5	16.0	1.1	230 (231)	nil	245 (256)
After treatment with oxygen at 400°	2.0	4.1	4.5	10.6	38.0	69 (125)	56	305 (280)
After treatment with nitrogen dioxide at 400°.	3.4	6.0	4.1	13.5	29.0	108 (211)	103	212 (213)
After treatment with superheated steam at 1000°.	nil	nil	0.4	0.4	75.0	nil (nil)	nil	364 (370)

TABLE III

Oxygen content, base adsorption capacity and bromine fixation of the 700°-degassed sugar charcoal before and after the various treatments

Description of the sample	Oxygen evolved on degassing at 1200° as:			Total oxygen evolved as CO ₂ , CO & H ₂ O on degassing at 1200°	Loss in weight during treatment	Base adsorption capacity	Non-titration CO ₂ -complex	Fixation of bromine
	(g./100 g.)							
	CO ₂	CO	H ₂ O					
Before any treatment	nil	2.5	0.8	3.3	—	nil (nil)	nil	396
After treatment with acidified pot. persulphate.	2.5	2.5	2.0	7.0	negligible	51 (156)	105	305 (291)
After treatment with chlorine water.	4.8	2.5	1.9	9.2	—	303 (300)	nil	395 (396)
After treatment with hydrogen peroxide	0.4	2.5	1.7	4.6	nil	22 (25)	3	405 (393)
After treatment with acidified pot. permanganate.	2.4	2.5	1.8	6.7	0.6	18 (150)	132	276 (264)
After treatment with oxygen at 400°.	3.0	1.9	2.0	6.9	31.0	74 (188)	114	302 (282)
After treatment with nitrogen dioxide at 400°.	2.9	2.0	2.2	7.1	22.0	32 (181)	149	242 (247)
After treatment with superheated steam at 1000°.	2.0	nil	1.5	3.5	62.0	20 (125)	103	281 (291)

TABLE IV

Oxygen content, base adsorption capacity and bromine fixation of the 1000° degassed sugar charcoal before and after the various treatment

Description of the sample	Oxygen evolved on degassing at 1200° as (g./100 g.)			Total oxygen evolved as CO ₂ , CO & H ₂ O on degassing at 1200° (g./100g.)	Loss in weight during treatment (g./100 g.)	Base adsorption capacity (m.e./100 g.)	Non-titratable CO ₂ -complex (m.e./100 g.)	Fixation of bromine (m.e./100 g.)
	CO ₂	CO	H ₂					
Before any treatment	nil	nil	nil	nil	—	nil (nil)	nil	398
After treatment with acidified pot. persulphate.	2.3	nil	1.8	4.1	negligible	19 (144)	123	278 (273)
After treatment with chlorine water.	6.1	0.6	2.0	8.7	—	205 (301)	176	218 (222)
After treatment with hydrogen peroxide.	5.3	nil	2.1	7.4	nil	40 (331)	291	110 (107)
After treatment with acidified pot. permanganate	2.8	0.4	1.4	4.6	0.3	27 (175)	148	215 (230)
After treatment with oxygen at 400°.	2.3	2.0	1.2	5.5	25.0	95 (143)	48	325 (350)
After treatment with nitrogen dioxide at 400°.	5.5	1.5	1.5	8.5	15.0	99 (344)	245	144 (153)
After treatment with superheated steam at 1000°.	2.0	nil	0.6	2.6	55.0	45 (125)	80	295 (318)

ROLE OF SUBSTRATE SYMMETRY IN GAS-SOLID REACTIONS. PART II: STRUCTURAL INTERPRETATION OF THE REACTIONS OF GASEOUS OXIDE

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The following figures (I and II) refer to the paper published in Journ. Indian Chem. Soc., Vol. 44, No 1, 1967. p. 4.

FIG. 1. The arrangement of oxygen (large circle) above and below a Th or U ion along the (111) Plane

FIG. 2 Showing diagrammatically the relation between the crystal structures of $\alpha\text{-UO}_2$ and CaUO_4 [$\text{Ca}(\text{UO}_2)_2$] The small shaded circles represent uranium atoms (after wells¹⁰)